

Reuse, recycling and refurbishment of furniture

The furniture industry is a front-runner in waste prevention and resource efficiency. Creative and novel concepts of upcycling of wood reinforce the reuse, recycling and refurbishment of furniture. Viable collection and retrieval schemes of resources are needed for commercialization and market uptake. Buy-back schemes can be a solution to retrieve back the goods sold.

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ Recovery of resources in buy-back systems can be well-controlled, which also provides options enhancing the quality of the product
- ▶ Buy-back can still be named innovative and a new circular approach. Test loops will need to confirm feasibility of the method in the near future.
- ▶ Buy-back can be a financially viable option while the quality of the back-received furniture can be better controlled.
- ▶ In a closed-loop system the company can gain great resource efficiency
- ▶ Product lifetime and customer loyalty can be enhanced as warranty and buy-back provides high certainty to the customers.

Regional coverage and transferability

The upcycling of waste wood into furniture takes already place across all Europe. The techno-economically feasible solutions depend on the local conditions, the policy framework and supporting schemes such as buy-back. This is not particularly regionally-bound although the reverse logistics and acceptance in the region do play a role. Generally, the centralized collection points for furniture are lacking. Most of the furniture ends up in bulky waste or are incinerated.

